

USING EAASI AND PROTOWEB TO RESTORE HYBRID INTERNET/CD-ROM ARTWORK “METABODY” BY STELARC

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Abstract – Emulation-as-a-Service Infrastructure (EAASI) is becoming a recognized tool for reanimating complex digital objects such as CD-ROM artworks. However, some CD-ROM artworks depend on now-obsolete websites as part of their dynamic interactions. We have been using Protoweb, a community driven project that restores early Internet services, to restore websites and revive the work’s Internet connectivity. This paper details the restoration of such a hybrid work by the Australian artist Stelarc and Merlin Integrated Media entitled “Metabody”.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The CD-ROM artwork “Metabody” was part of a case study addressed in the ARC Linkage Project *Archiving Australian Media Arts: Towards a Method and National Collection* (AAMA), led by Melanie Swalwell. [1] This project worked with key cultural institutions to conserve media art case studies from their archives to develop good practices for the preservation of digital media arts heritage. [2] The work is also featured in The Australian Emulation Network. [3]

This artwork is part of the Griffith University Art Museum (GUAM) collection of media artworks

contained on CD-ROM. “Metabody” is the most complex of the 18 GUAM artworks examined in the project, and the last. Preserving this 1997 Macintosh hybrid media artwork proved an intriguing puzzle that revealed intricate restoration requirements.

The 1997 websites for Merlin Integrated Media and Stelarc have long disappeared. Fortunately, several versions have been saved by the Wayback Machine of the Internet Archive. Using Protoweb, we collected the best instance and restored it in the Protoweb servers. Configuring Netscape Navigator enabled us to connect the CD-ROM to this vintage website and explore the complex interactions once again.

II. THE STRUCTURE OF THE CD-ROM

The ReadMe file on this CD-ROM informs the user: “Metabody is a hybrid CD-ROM/Website. Certain sections within Metabody allow you to interact with the Internet from the CD-ROM. However, the bulk of Metabody will operate without an Internet connection.”

The CD-ROM is composed of two types of interactive nodes. “Local elements” work on the computer without having to connect to the Web. Some of the local elements are the archive of locally created golems, and the archive of locally created assemblages – both of which use VRML 2.0 programming of the RealVR plug-in. Golems, in the

Metabody universe, are 3-dimensional shape constructions the user can make and save.

VRML, or Virtual Reality Modeling Language, was a 3D graphics file format and scripting language for the Web. It was designed to let people build and explore interactive 3D worlds inside a web browser. RealVR is a 3D virtual reality plugin and authoring system designed to complement VRML by offering a more accessible way to create and view interactive 3D environments on the web. VRML failed because consumer computers were not powerful enough to render these 3D graphics smoothly, and Internet connections were too slow to keep up with the large files. The browser plug-ins were also quirky and difficult to find and install, as I was to later discover.

The CD-ROM also has 9 remote elements that interact with the Web in different ways. Each uses a specialized browser plug-in such as QuickTime, Shockwave, VRML 1.0 plus Live3D, and VRML 2.0 plus RealVR. These remote elements are Stelarc conceptions realized by Merlin Integrated Media. Some of the elements were meant to connect to and activate Stelarc's body in live performances using a "net-connected computer muscle stimulation system," while others read from and write traces to the Stelarc website for later visitors to add to and experience. Some of these remote elements also have local instantiations, which will work on the user's computer without an Internet connection.

The splash page of the CD-ROM has two primary links, leading to two different ways of navigating around the same CD-ROM contents. The two links, "[Sigma] wave" and "site" point to the same content with different navigation pathways. There is also hidden content that can only be found through circuitous pathways. This includes a biography of Stelarc, short videos of classic performances, some of his writings and interviews, and a bibliography. Another section has an interactive timeline of historic automatons and robots. The "site" side is an organic-looking map with links to each of these artfully produced interactives or information pages.

III. PREPARING THE EMULATION ENVIRONMENT

CD-ROM artworks can no longer be interacted with on contemporary 2025 computers. Before the CD-ROM could be used, an appropriate emulation environment had to be created. This CD-ROM included a ReadMe file with detailed optimal technical requirements for the CD-ROM to work

properly. These requirements are much more elaborate than most media artworks require. In addition to a PowerMac processor of 132 or better and Macintosh System 7.5.3 or later, it also asked for typical requirements such as 16-bit color depth and 32 megs of RAM. Other more complex setup instructions included changing the Macintosh 3 Speech Manager voice to 'Ralph,' having Netscape Navigator 3.0 or 3.1 installed. It also asked for Quicktime (2.1 or later) and Shockwave (with no version indicated). Other plug-ins were included on the CD-ROM: Winsock Netmanage Lib, RealVR Traveller plug-in, and RealVR Playback Xtra, all noted with specific places in the Macintosh operating system where they must be placed.

I experienced a significant problem with my assumptions when setting up this environment. System 7.5.3 or later indicated an operating system that was released in January 1996. "Metabody" is copyright 1997. ReadMe asks for a version of Netscape Navigator at 3.0 or 3.1, but there does not seem to be a version 3.1 of Navigator; later releases were 3.01 and 3.04; then Netscape Navigator 4.0 was released in June 1997.

I assumed that later versions of these operating systems and programs would work just as well if not better. This is often the case, where backward compatibility is assumed in popular programs and operating systems. I chose the later Macintosh OS 9.0.4, the last operating system version that works in the Sheepshaver emulator managed in EAASI. I upgraded Quicktime to version 5.05, and Shockwave to version 8.0. I also installed Netscape Communicator 4.8, instead of the recommended Netscape 3.0 or 3.1. This environment worked at first glance but ultimately did not render the Live3D-dependent items and seemed to be having trouble with other 3D renderings as well.

Further research showed that Live3D only shipped with Netscape Navigator 3; with the upgrade to Netscape Communicator 4.0, Live3D support was removed. Even deeper research found that every example of Netscape Navigator 3.x that I found on the web – at the Internet Archive [4] as well as Macintosh abandonware sites Macintosh Garden [5] and Macintosh Repository [6] -- did not include Live3D. I installed each version in turn and looked for Live3D in the "Plug Ins" folder. Live3D wasn't there. Instead, installing Netscape included an option to install additional plug-ins, with a download link that

neither worked nor was preserved on the Wayback Machine. [7] I also found that Roeck's thorough paper about web browser characterization and preservation does not mention Live3D. [8] It seemed a mystery to locate.

My next step seemed to be a long slog trawling through unindexed Macintosh VRML training and tools CD-ROMs, until I found a Microsoft Edge pointer to an Internet Archive resource called "Live 3D installers." [9] That I couldn't find this resource searching the Internet Archive directly seems to be an artifact of their search algorithm, which does not see "live3d" and "live 3d" as the same search, and also does not do a string search for "live 3d" but rather looks for the two individual words, netting too many false drops.

Searching after the fact, I discovered that I could have found this plug-in by using the advanced search by putting quote marks around "live 3d," but I did not think of that during my several search sessions. Note that the search "live 3d" also nets the title "Gameloft Live! 3D (Android Version)" – showing that the archive.org advanced search also elides the "!". Software naming peculiarities are not well-served by general search algorithms that treat spaces and special characters differently from general text.

With a fresh environment made using Macintosh OS 9.0.4, Netscape Navigator 3.04 from Macintosh Garden, Shockwave 8.0, and the Live3D plug-in installed, I added the Metabody CD-ROM image from GUAM. With that, I changed the voice to 'Ralph' and installed the Winsock and RealVR plug-ins included in the "appendages" folder of the CD-ROM per the ReadMe instructions.

The CD-ROM, once properly installed in the emulated operating system, seemed to be navigating, playing sound, and activating its various interactives in an appropriate manner, i.e., it looked like it "worked."

IV. COLLECTING THE WEBSITE AND PREPARING IN PROTOWEB

For other projects the Digital Heritage Lab has been experimenting with a service called Protoweb. [10] Protoweb is a free public service that hosts historical Internet websites to demonstrate the Internet in its early days. It is a community driven project consisting of volunteers with the goal of rebuilding and restoring early Internet services to offer a seamless browsing experience. The service

Figure 1: Golem Option Page

hosts countless mid to late 1990s websites with downloads, games, and other resources fully working. As of 2025, the service is in Public Beta and currently going through a substantial development phase as they build the tools and documentation to support the service, while concurrently working on their extensive library of classic websites and resources.

Protoweb includes a tool to harvest websites with specific dates from the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine. Anyone can look at these sites or become a contributor. Protoweb enforces specific requirements for restored websites, such as completeness of the site and its links. To restore a site, a confirmed contributor searches the Wayback Machine for a desired URL in an appropriate date range, chooses one that looks complete, and sets the WARNICK Website Recovery Tool to work harvesting the domain. Once done, the contributor checks the pages for quality, then can publish the downloaded site to the Protoweb server.

The growing suite of Protoweb preserved Web pages is available on a contemporary machine using the Protoweb or RetroZilla browsers. The pages are also available to vintage browsers, with appropriately configured proxy, while running on vintage hardware or in emulation.

I configured the proxy in the Netscape Navigator 3.04 used in this restoration to point to the appropriate server: wayback.protoweb.org through port 7851. For this project we were still using the experimental EAASI tool, which will only connect to the Internet using the administrative console. So, the remainder of my work was through this side of the EAASI tool, a different interface to the same

metadata, though it has some different views and capabilities.

The CD-ROM nodes link to specific websites. The splash page of the CD-ROM shows <http://www.metabody.com> as the project website. I found other sites by exploring the different links, and noting along the bottom bar of Netscape what address it was trying to go to. Other important sites were <http://www.merlin.com.au/metabody/>, which the above link sometimes would resolve to, as well as <http://www.stelarc.com.au/>, Stelarc's personal website.

The Wayback Machine had many save dates particularly of www.merlin.com.au, and I began to despair again, this time not being able to figure out which of the many saved sites was the most complete. We communicated with the artist, Stelarc, who did not have a copy of the original website in his personal collection. After searching for several collaborators, we were referred to two Wayback Machine saves that were confirmed to be the most complete specific date saves of <http://www.merlin.com.au/> and <http://www.merlin.com.au/stelarc/>, and these are the versions that I saved and published using Protoweb tools.

The emulated CD-ROM now successfully linked to these Protoweb-preserved websites. Now to see whether the various interactive animations worked.

V. EXPLORING THE CD-ROM CAPABILITIES

Early emulations which I built in the flawed emulation environment did not work well; the animations did not activate, and certain modules either did not respond or showed the 'broken plug-in' image. Once I managed to build a complete environment by systematically following the crucial ReadMe file included with the CD-ROM, the modules behaved more richly and predictably.

Again, several of the remote elements also had a local option. For example, the *Being Generator* has two options, "inner website" and "generator." Inner website starts up and the golem builder works, and these golems can be "grafted," or saved to the local hard drive; the work, however, requires an Internet connection to the Web to "upload to the website as a lone golem. In the past, this would add the

Figure 2: URL Body page

individually-created golems to the live website, making it a participatory work in collaboration with the audience. I am still working with Protoweb to enable writing to the website, which requires permissions and CGI bash script tools that we have not created yet. So *Being Generator* is best experienced using its local instance, with the promise that future technical developments will bring better connectivity to the website.

URL Body is the module that uses VRML 1.0 in conjunction with the elusive Live3D plug-in. This page includes a working rotating body, which can be activated, rotated, and undergo "mitosis" or doubling, in the red circle on the right. The bottom right grid of buttons activate zoom in and out, as well as rotating the body in three dimensions.

The CD-ROM tells us "The URL body evolves to log files of the Stelarc website. Log files, as records of remote viewings, transmute the code which defines the body icon as a composite of VRML cells. Each cell, for the moment arbitrarily linked to a node within the Stelarc site, is mutable according to its node's log file record. The intention has been to implement an

Figure 3: Ping Body diagram

abstract and collective data-visualizing ‘metavar’, in contrast to a personal avatar. The metavar, recording the variable ebbs and flows of interest in different nodes, allows URL passers-by to leave a reconfigured trace of their visit.”

Clicking on the *URL body* website link opens a new Netscape page on the www.merlin.com.au page, which downloads a file, *spinbody3_b.wrl*, from the vintage web connection mediated via Protoweb. The file extension *.wrl* is linked to Live3D. Although *spinbody3_b.wrl* does not open in the frame it is intended to, once downloaded it opens with Netscape Navigator, revealing a body that responds to a set of Live3D controls such as walk, spin, look, slide, and point; as well as changing the lighting on the 3 dimensional figure. Once again, I have been unable to activate the final function of writing to the log file on the Stelarc website.

The third of nine and last remote element I will look at is *Ping Body*. The *Ping Body* module also has options for *Live Connection* and *Simulation*, with the addition of a *Background* page. The *Live Connection* requires the Shockwave plug-in. When clicked, the browser points to the *Ping Body* page at merlin.com.au, which is now inactive. At the time it connected to probes on Stelarc’s body which interacted with the IP address of clicks in live performances.

The *Simulation* link is another local animated page of body parts which responds to clicks by simulating IP addresses and URLs and animating wireframe body parts.

The *Background* page is text about the work, reading:

The *Ping Body* performance produces a powerful inversion of the usual interface of the body to the Net. Instead of collective bodies determining the operation of the Internet, the collective Internet activity moves the body. The Internet becomes not merely a mode of information transmission, but also a transducer, effecting physical action.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has emphasized the technical aspects of restoring or recreating the functionality of this complex hybrid CD-ROM and Internet artwork. I want to draw attention to the incredible technical virtuosity that went into the links, music, artwork, videos, and interactives that bring to the user a real experience of Stelarc’s deeply embodied conceptual framework.

The work of Stelarc continuously calls into question the relationship of “the body”, his body, to other people and structures in the world. In this case, varieties of mediation between the body and his body to the machinations of the Internet.

This written technical analysis of *Metabody* is necessarily limited; to really appreciate the work the audience needs to be able to interact with this CD-ROM, exploring its various nodes and interactions. However, the restoration of this work using configured environments mediated by EaaSI and Protoweb brings us one step closer to this hopeful future of preserving born digital cultural heritage.

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